

Cross-Coupling of Mo- and V-Nitrogenases Permits Protein-Mediated Protection from Oxygen Deactivation

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Abstract: Nitrogenases catalyze dinitrogen (N₂) fixation to ammonia (NH₃). While these enzymes are highly sensitive to deactivation by molecular oxygen (O₂) they can be produced by obligate aerobes for diazotrophy, necessitating a mechanism by which nitrogenase can be protected from deactivation. In the bacterium *Azotobacter vinelandii*, one mode of such protection involves an O₂-responsive ferredoxin-type protein ("Shethna protein II", or "FeSII") which is thought to bind with Mo-dependent nitrogenase's two component proteins (NifH and NifDK) to form a catalytically stalled yet O₂-tolerant tripartite protein complex. This protection mechanism has been reported for Mo-nitrogenase, however, *in vitro* assays with V-nitrogenase suggest that this mechanism is not universal to the three known nitrogenase isoforms. Here we report that the reductase of the V-nitrogenase (VnfH) can engage in this FeSII-mediated protection mechanism when cross-coupled with Mo-nitrogenase NifDK. Interestingly, the cross-coupling of the Mo-nitrogenase reductase NifH with the V-nitrogenase VnfDGK protein does not yield such protection.

Introduction

Fixed N in the form of NH₃ in fertilizers has been used to feed a growing amount of the world population ever since the process was developed. While humans, animals and most plants need to feed themselves with fixed nitrogen sources, some bacteria and archaea can fix atmospheric N₂ to form NH₃ which can be used by other organisms to synthesize the necessary building blocks. The diazotrophic bacterium *Azotobacter vinelandii*, an obligate aerobe, can fix N₂ the any of the three nitrogenase isoforms: Mo-, V- and Fe-dependent nitrogenase.^[1; 2] Mo-nitrogenase consists of a homodimeric reductase protein (NifH, also the "Fe protein", existing physiologically as NifH₂) and a substrate-reducing NifDK protein (also known as the MoFe protein, physiologically a Nif(DK)₂ (αβ)₂ heterotetramer). Similarly, V-nitrogenase consists of the VnfH reductase and a

substrate-reducing VnfDGK protein (or the "VFe protein", physiologically a Vnf(DGK)₂ (αβγ)₂ heterohexamer); similarly, Fe-only nitrogenase consists of an AnfH reductase and a substrate-reducing AnfDGK protein (or the "FeFe protein", physiologically an Anf(DGK)₂ (αβγ)₂ heterohexamer).^[1-4] In VnfDGK and AnfDGK, the γ subunits are bound to the α subunits of the protein and are thought to play a role in substrate selectivity as well as cofactor selection and insertion.^[5; 6]

NifH contains a [4Fe-4S] cubane cluster bridging the two subunits and two MgATP-binding sites (one per monomer). During transient association of NifH to NifDK (or VnfDGK/AnfDGK protein), electron transfer from the [4Fe-4S] cluster of NifH is coupled to the hydrolysis of 2MgATP^[7] Within NifDK, a [8Fe-7S] P cluster ultimately facilitates electron transfer from NifH to the site of substrate reduction, a catalytic cofactor [7Fe-9S-Mo-C]:homocitrate ("FeMoco") with M being Mo, V or Fe, depending on the nitrogenase isoform.^[7; 8]

Figure 1. X-ray crystal structure of Mo-dependent nitrogenase (PDB: 4WZA) with the NifDK (light blue and pink) and two NifH proteins (grey) in a transition

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state-like complex. Atom color scheme: C = grey, Fe = rust, Mo = cyan, O = red, S = yellow.

The presence of the γ subunit and its role in catalysis could suggest greater similarities between VnfDGK and AnfdGK. To the contrary, Trncik *et al.* demonstrated that the cross compatibility between the reductases and catalytic protein is greater between the Mo- and V-nitrogenases than with Fe-nitrogenase.^[9] While the peptide sequences of NifH and VnfH from *A. vinelandii* share 91% sequence homology (and 95% positive amino acid matching, i.e. amino acids were replaced with other bearing side chains with similar properties) Fig. S2), only 60% sequence similarity exists between NifH and AnfH (although important structural features for nitrogenase activity are conserved).^[9] Figure 2 highlights the global similarity in conformation of the NifH and VnfH proteins from their X-ray crystal structures. Perhaps the greatest difference in conformation is found at the C-terminal region, the opposite end of the protein with respect to the NifH:NifDK binding interface. This overall similarity could explain the similar specific activities of the NifDK and VnfDGK proteins when coupled with AnfH.^[9]

Since the 1960's it has been known that Mo-nitrogenases are sensitive to deactivation by molecular oxygen (O₂).^[10] Given the overall similarities between the three isoforms, it is therefore expected that all three nitrogenases might exhibit similar sensitivities towards

Figure 2. Overlay of NifH₂ (beige, 6N4L^[11]) and VnfH₂ (blue, 6Q93^[12]) from *A. vinelandii*. The largest conformational differences are mostly observed at the C-term.

deactivation by O₂. In 2015, Schlesier *et al.* confirmed that NifH exhibits far greater sensitive to O₂ than the NifDK protein during *in vitro* deactivation assays, which can be explained by the surface-exposed nature of the [4Fe-4S] cluster rendering it accessible to O₂, in contrast to the relatively buried P cluster and FeMoco of NifDK.^[13] By extension, this is also expected to

be the case for the VnfH and AnfH reductases. Despite this O₂-sensitivity, *A. vinelandii* is an obligate aerobe, and thus, at least one mechanism must exist to protect the produced nitrogenases from O₂-mediated deactivation. In the 1960s, Dervartanian *et al.* discovered a protein homodimer carrying two [2Fe-2S] clusters (termed FeSII herein). This ferredoxin-like FeSII has been extensively characterized and is thought to protect Mo-nitrogenase from O₂-mediated deactivation by locking one NifDK and one NifH in an inactive-yet-protected NifH:FeSII:NifDK complex, which can then be unlocked upon reduction and resume activity. Interestingly, *A. vinelandii* produces FeSII under both diazotrophic and non-diazotrophic conditions (FeSII production is upregulated 2.5-fold under diazotrophy).^[13-19] It is hypothesized that this protein can be found in an "open" or "closed" conformation, although recent results suggest that crystallographic artifacts may explain this the apparent conformations of the FeSII protein (and that such extensive changes in conformation may not be necessary).^[13] To the best of our knowledge, a single study has reported on the possible role of the FeSII protein in protecting V-nitrogenase from *A. vinelandii*; significant protection against deactivation by O₂ was not observed *in vitro*, although these assays were performed in complex cell-free lysates and not on purified components.^[18]

Here, we investigate *in vitro* FeSII-mediated protection of V-nitrogenases against O₂ using purified component proteins. We confirm that the combination of VnfH with the VnfDGK protein does not result in significant protection in the presence of the FeSII protein (under conditions where protection is afforded to the NifH and NifDK proteins). Interestingly, the cross-coupling of the NifDK with VnfH (such cross-coupling yields enzymatic activity^[9]) results in FeSII-dependent protection for both H₂ and NH₃ production. In contrast, VnfDGK does not engage in FeSII-mediated protection with either VnfH or NifH; we hypothesize that this is due to the additional VnfG subunit of VnfDGK.

Results and Discussion

The FeSII protein does not protect VnfH/VnfDGK from O₂-mediated deactivation *in vitro*.

The FeSII protein was heterologously produced in *E. coli*, as reported previously (Fig. S1).^[13; 20] Strep-tagged NifDK and VnfDGK proteins were purified from *A. vinelandii* strains DJ2102 and DJ2253; NifH (strain RS1) and VnfH (strain DJ2225) were purified as reported previously.^[21] Standard O₂-protection assays using NifDK and NifH were carried out under Ar (Fig. 3) and N₂ (Fig. S6), where exposure to 2% O₂ in the vial headspace for 10 minutes results in oxidative damage (no significant activity was detected). Including the FeSII protein during this treatment phase enables Mo-nitrogenase to retain 59% activity for H₂ production (under Ar and N₂) and 69% NH₃ production activity (under these assay conditions).

These O₂-protection assays were next performed using purified VnfH and VnfDGK proteins; as shown in Fig. 3, virtually no H⁺-

reduction activity was observed after 20 minutes of O₂ treatment in the presence of the FeSII protein (also for H₂ and NH₃ production under N₂, Fig. S6). The location of the affinity tag on VnfDGK (N-term of VnfK) is not expected to interfere with the VnfH/FeSII binding interface. Importantly, the presence of FeSII in the absence of O₂ does not alter Mo- and V-nitrogenase activity assays under these conditions (Fig. S5). Taking the case of NifH:NifDK as an example, we hypothesize that VnfH is also more sensitive to O₂ deactivation than VnfDGK^[13]. To date, an experimental structure of the NifH:FeSII:NifDK complex has not been reported, although structural models have been predicted.^[13; 22] The models for FeSII binding propose interactions between the FeSII protein, NifH and NifD of the NifDK protein. The presence of the additional γ VnfG subunit on the side of VnfD^[8] in VnfDGK may therefore impede the ability of the FeSII protein to form an analogous complex with V-nitrogenase, thus resulting in O₂ damage. VnfG is thought to participate in substrate and cofactor selection due to its proximity to the FeVco channel.^[5] The predictive models show the binding of FeSII protein close to this specific site, thus, we hypothesize that VnfG and FeSII may well be mutually exclusive.

Figure 3: Unlike Mo-nitrogenase, V-nitrogenase does not benefit from protection against O₂ deactivation by the FeSII protein. Nitrogenase protection assays for Mo- and V-dependent nitrogenase under 1 atm Ar. Proton (H⁺) reduction activity to H₂ was measured by GC-TCD. Residual activity after 20 minutes O₂ exposition is shown as % remaining activity for a standard assay with 1:1 NifH:NifDK without O₂ treatment.

Cross-coupling VnfH with NifDK enables FeSII-mediated protection against O₂.

We tested this hypothesis by examining cross-reactivity between the Mo- and V-nitrogenases. As confirmed in Fig. 4 and in Fig. S7, cross-coupling NifH:VnfDGK and VnfH:NifDK (this hybrid nitrogenase system has shown even greater activity

than standard Mo-dependent Nitrogenase for N₂ reduction^[9]) also results in H₂ production activity (in 1 atm Ar) under these assay conditions. Fig. 4 and Fig. S6' confirm that the FeSII protein engages in protein-mediated protection when NifDK is coupled to VnfH (for both H₂ and NH₃ production); importantly, such protection is not afforded when NifH is cross-coupled with VnfDGK, further supporting our hypothesis that VnfG interferes with the binding of the FeSII protein. We hypothesize that AnfG may also prevent FeSII protein interactions; further, the cross-coupling of AnfH with NifDK is non-reactive due to proposed differences in surface charges.^[5]

NifEN cannot replace NifDK in FeSII-mediated protection from O₂.

With FeSII being a [2Fe-2S] ferredoxin-like protein produced under non-diazotrophic conditions, it is challenging to propose an alternative to the FeSII protein that has been specifically evolved for the protection of V-nitrogenase. Nevertheless, *A. vinelandii* grows diazotrophically using V-nitrogenase alone, thus, V-nitrogenase must partially tolerate O₂ in this obligate aerobe. One explanation is that FeSII plays a minor physiological role in protein-mediated protection against O₂, with oxidative phosphorylation and mucus secretion carrying a greater burden^[14; 23]. This could also explain why FeSII is also produced under non-diazotrophic conditions: perhaps O₂-protection by FeSII is not its only (or primary) physiological role. While our data for nitrogenase protection by FeSII upon the cross-coupling of VnfH:NifDK could afford a means by which the more sensitive VnfH component could be protected from O₂ (knowing that VnfH:VnfDGK does not engage in a complex with FeSII), we consider this to be unlikely since the *nif* system takes over from the *nif* system in the absence of Mo and presence of V. While a leaky *nif* promoter could counter this argument, *in vivo* quantities of NifDK would nevertheless be expected to be limited. Further, *A. vinelandii* strain DJ2253 from which we purified VnfDGK is $\Delta nifDK$ thus, such a mechanism cannot be solely responsible^[24].

NifH plays a multitude of roles during nitrogenase production, maturation and activity which require protein-protein interactions^[25; 26]. One such activity is the maturation of the FeMoco on NifEN^[27] prior to transfer to NifDK, a NifH-dependent activity. We this in-mind, we speculated that NifH and FeSII may engage in alternative tripartite (and protective) protein complexes to preserve the activity of NifH, such as with NifEN (NifH:FeSII:NifEN). In support of this idea, an *A. vinelandii* strain lacking NifDK ($\Delta nifDK$, unpublished) yields active NifH protein^[28] that could not have engaged in a NifH:FeSII:NifDK protective complex *in vivo*. In the case of V-nitrogenase, the formation of a protective VnfH:FeSII:VnfEN complex could possibly serve to protect VnfH irrespective of the presence of VnfG on the VnfDGK protein. Further experimentation is required to determine if this is indeed the case.

To address this, we performed FeSII nitrogenase O₂-protection assays where NifDK was replaced with a stoichiometric quantity of holo-NifEN from *A. vinelandii*; following exposure to O₂, one

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equivalent of NifDK was added alongside dithionite to initiate regular nitrogenase turnover under 1 atm Ar. We observed that the activity of NifH was abolished in all repeats ($n = 3$) and conclude that a protective NifH:FeSII:NifEN complex does not form *in vitro*. We therefore expect that such a protective complex is not relevant *in vivo* and that this likely also extends to V-nitrogenase.

Figure 4: Cross-coupling VnfH with NifDK enables FeSII-mediated protection. Hybrid VnfH:NifDK protection assays using FeSII protein under Ar and N₂ were performed at a 1:1 molar ratio of VnfH:NifDK. Treatment with 2% O₂ in the vial headspace was performed for 20 minutes in the absence or presence of FeSII (1 molar equivalent).

Conclusion

We confirm that purified VnfH and VnfDGK component proteins of V-nitrogenase do not engage in FeSII-mediated protection against deactivation by O₂ *in vitro*. Interestingly, the cross-coupling of VnfH with NifDK does permit such protection in the presence of FeSII; however, this is not afforded when NifH is cross-coupled with VnfDGK. We hypothesize that the presence of the VnfG subunit on the VnfDGK protein inhibits interactions with the FeSII protein. We hypothesize that FeSII-mediated protection plays a minor role in protecting nitrogenases from deactivation by O₂^[29; 30]. Protective assays performed using NifEN suggest that the FeSII protein does not engage in an analogous FeSII protection complex using NifEN in the place of NifDK.

Experimental Section

General: All chemicals were purchased from Merck (Sigma Aldrich) and used without further treatment (unless specifically stated). The synthetic gene used of the production of FeSII was ordered from GeneArt™ with overhangs for pET21a insertion.

General cloning work was performed using Phusion™ High-Fidelity polymerase in a MiniAmp™. The FeSII gene was inserted into the pET21a vector using the GeneArt™ Gibson Assembly kit (Thermo Fisher Scientific). The resulting pET21a_FeSII plasmid was chemically transformed into competent *E. coli* DH5α, from which the plasmid was extracted using Macherey Nagel's Midi Prep Plus Kit. Isolated plasmid was transformed into chemically competent *E. coli* C43(DE3) cells (Merck) for FeSII production, as reported previously^[13; 15]. *E. coli* LB plates were grown on standard LB medium (Carl Roth) plates at 37 °C with 100 µg/mL ampicillin (Applichem) for selection.

***E. coli* culturing and FeSII protein purification:** FeSII was produced based on previously reported methods^[13; 15]. A 70 mL starting culture of LB media was inoculated with frozen stocks of *E. coli* C43(DE3) containing pET21a_FeSII and cultivated aerobically at 37 °C/200 rpm overnight. Larger culture volumes of LB media containing 50 mM ferric ammonium citrate were inoculated with the overnight starting culture (2 % v/v) and grown under the same conditions (in baffled 5 L flasks) until reaching an OD_{600 nm} of 0.6. FeSII gene expression was then induced with 200 µM IPTG (final concentration, Applichem) from a 1 M stock solution. The culture was then incubated for 5 hours at 30 °C. The cells were then harvested at 4'800 x g with a SL40 centrifuge (Thermo Fisher Scientific) with TX-750 rotor for 15 min and stored at -80 °C.

While the FeSII protein can be purified under oxic conditions, FeSII was purified here within an anoxic glovebox (95:5 N₂:H₂, COY Laboratory Products, MI USA) in the absence of additional reductants. *E. coli* cell paste was resuspended in 50 mM acetate buffer (pH 5.2) and lysed by ultrasonification (50% amplification, 2 seconds on/off cycles, for 20 minutes, CL18 with 6.4 mm probe tip (Qsonica), FB120 (Fisherbrand)). Lysed cells were centrifuged at 30'000 x g for 1 hour at 4 °C. The red supernatant was then loaded on a cationic exchange column HiTrap™ SP HP (Cytiva) and FeSII was eluted with a linear NaCl gradient of 0-100 mM over 7 column volumes with a flowrate of 5 mL/min. The red FeSII -containing fraction was then passed over a HiPrep™ 26/60 Sephacryl S-300HR column (Cytiva) with a flowrate of 2.3 mL/min to obtain pure FeSII protein. FeSII was concentrated using an Amicon® stirred cell under 5 bar N₂ (5.0) using an Ultracel® 3 kDa cutoff membrane (Merck Millipore).

Cultivation of *A. vinelandii* strains and purification of nitrogenase proteins: Strep-tagged NifDK (*A. vinelandii* strain DJ2102, tag on the N-term of NifD^[31]), strep-tagged VnfDGK (*A. vinelandii* strain DJ2253, tag on the N-term of VnfK^[24]), untagged NifH (*A. vinelandii* strain RS1^[32]) and VnfH (*A. vinelandii* strain DJ2225, derived from DJ1254^[33]) were obtained based on published protocols. All *A. vinelandii* cultures were grown on a modified Burke's medium (all salt concentrations) and supplemented with either 6.4 µM Na₂MoO₄·2H₂O or 20 µM NaVO₃. After overnight growth of main cultures (4x 3 L cultures, 5 L baffled flasks, 200 rpm) and once the cultures had reached an OD_{600 nm} of 2, cells were harvested

by centrifugation (15 minutes, 4800 x g) and gently resuspended in NH₃Cl-free medium for *nif* or *vnf* derepression for 3-4 hours. Cells were harvested by centrifugation (15 minutes, 4800 x g), flash frozen, and stored at -80 °C until use.

Briefly, frozen cells were transferred inside of the anoxic chamber and thawed/resuspended using a Tris:HCl buffer pH 8 (50 mM, 10 mM DT, 37 % v/v glycerol). The cells were pelleted by centrifugation in gastight bottles (25 minutes, 12'000 x g) and lysed by osmotic shock (rapid resuspension in the same Tris:HCl buffer lacking glycerol). Strep-tagged NifDK or VnfDGK proteins were purified over 5 mL StrepTrap™ XT column (Cytiva) with a flowrate of 5 mL/min, and eluted using Tris:HCl buffer (50 mM, pH 8, containing 300 mM NaCl and 50 mM biotin). NifDK and VnfDGK were concentrated and stored at >10 mg/mL in liquid N₂ until use. NifH or VnfH were purified by loading the StrepTrap™ column flow-through fraction on a 20 mL HiPrep™ Q HP 16/10 anion exchange column. Both proteins were eluted with a linear 200-650 mM NaCl gradient over 7 column volumes with a flowrate of 5 mL/min. Brown fractions containing NifH or VnfH were pooled and concentrated using an Amicon® stirred cell under 5 bar 5.0 N₂ using an Ultracel® 30 kDa cutoff membrane. Concentrated protein was then loaded using a 10 mL Superloop™ over a HiPrep™ 26/60 Sephacryl S-300HR column (Cytiva) with a flowrate of 2.3 mL/min to obtain pure NifH/VnfH. Proteins were concentrated and stored at >25 mg/mL in Liquid N₂ until use. Standard H₂ production activity assays with a 16:1 ratio of NifH:NifDK or VnfH:VnfDGK were performed to validate the integrity of the purified proteins (Fig. S4). NifEN (shared by the Rubio group) was prepared as previously reported.^[27]

Nitrogenase activity assays: All activity assays were initially prepared in an anoxic glovebox under an Ar atmosphere (<2 ppm O₂, Jacomex, France). A master assay solution was prepared in 100 mM MOPS (pH 7, Applichem) and contained: 30 mM creatine phosphate (Roche), 5 mM ATP and degassed for >3 hours by rapid stirring inside of the glovebox. Immediately prior to use, bovine serum albumin (1.3 mg/mL), creatine phosphokinase (0.2 mg/mL, from rabbit muscle, Roche) and MgCl₂ (10 mM [final]) was added. Glass Wheaton® serum vials (13 mL volume) were then filled with 1 mL of this assay solution.

“Standard” NifH:NifDK or VnfH:VnfDGK activity assays were performed by omitting MgCl₂ from the assay solution and including dithionite (10 mM). These assays were initiated by the addition of MgCl₂ (10 mM [final] from a 1 M stock solution) and terminated by the addition of 300 µL of 400 mM EDTA (pH 7) after 8 minutes of reaction in a shaking water bath (30 °C).

O₂ protection assays included 10 mM MgCl₂ (dithionite was omitted) and all required proteins were added to the 1 mL reaction with 0.83 nmol of each protein (1:1:1 ratio). For reference, the molecular weight of NifDK was considered to be 240 kDa. Crimp-sealed vials were brought outside of the glovebox for gas treatment. All vials were vented to atmospheric pressure prior to initiating the enzymatic assays. A 2 % O₂

atmosphere was obtained by the addition of pure O₂ using a gastight syringe (Precision Sampling A-2 series, Merck). The vials were incubated with shaking at 30 °C for 20 minutes, and then the vial atmosphere was replaced with either Ar (5.0) or N₂ (4.5) by vacuum/flush cycles and vented to atmospheric pressure prior to initiating the nitrogenase assays by the addition of dithionite (20 mM [final], 1 M stock solution). The assays were terminated after 8 minutes as described above.

H₂ was quantified on an 8610C gas chromatograph (SRI Instruments) using Ar as the carrier gas and a thermal conductivity detector. NH₃ was measured by the ortho-phthalaldehyde (OPA) assay, as described previously.^[20; 32; 34]

Supporting Information

The authors have cited additional references within the Supporting Information.^[35-37]

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((Data Availability and Conflicts of Interest statements are generated automatically from information in Editorial Manager!))

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The FeSII (or “Shethna”) protein from *Azotobacter vinelandii* can protect the Mo-dependent nitrogenase system from O₂ damage. Here, we confirm that V-dependent nitrogenase does not benefit from this mechanism (shown *in vitro*). Interestingly, cross-coupling V- and Mo-nitrogenase proteins enables FeSII-mediated protection.

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